

Recyclable Structural Supercapacitor Composite with Polymer-Ionic Liquid Electrolyte

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Structures & Composite Materials
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Structural Composite Energy Storage Device

- **Increasing the efficiency and sustainability**
 - Weight
 - Power supply system performance
 - Recyclability
- **Optimizing individual subsystems**
 - Limited saving
- **A holistic approach**
 - Multifunctional composites
 - Electrically active structural material
 - Recyclable components

State of the Art Multifunctional Structural Energy Storage Composites

Ganguly, A. et al., ACS Appl. Energy Mater. 2020, 3, 5, 4245–4254

- Graphene nanoflake carbon fibre
- Ionic liquid
- Epoxy

Ding, Y. et al., Energy Fuels 2022, 36, 2171–2178

- Activated woven carbon fibre
- Ionic liquid
- Epoxy

Qian H. et al., ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces 2013, 5, 13, 6113–6122

- Carbon aerogel carbon fibre
- Ionic liquid
- Epoxy

Asp, L. E., Adv. Energy Sustainability Res. 2021, 2, 2000093

- Carbon fibre
- Lithium salt
- Bisphenol a ethoxylate dimethacrylate

Challenges

Thermosets

Objective

- Incorporation of the sustainability and recyclability in the design
- Designing the appropriate material system and compatible recycling method

Electrolyte-Synthesis Process

- Combining thermoplastic polymers with ionic liquids:
 - recyclable, high conductivity, good mechanical performance electrolyte
- *In-situ* polymerization at room temperature

Material Selection- Compatibility Study

- Flory- Huggins's parameter, χ
 - **Cohesive** force (in polymer) vs. **Adhesive** force (polymer and ionic liquid)
 - Polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) and Ionic liquid (EMIM-TFSI)

Proposed material system

**Langer, E., et al. "Essential quality parameters of plasticizers." Plasticizers derived from post-consumer PET (2020): 45-100.*

**Mohan, M., et al. Green Chem., 2022, 24, 1165*

**Yoo, B., et al. Ind. Eng. Chem. Res. 2012, 51, 29, 9913–9917*

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Electrolyte Synthesis Process

- Polymer: Elium 188 O resin (Methyl methacrylate, MMA)
- Ionic liquid: EMIM-TFSI
- Initiator: Dibenzoyl peroxide (1.6% w/w)
- Lithium salt (Li-TFSI)
- Fumed silica (SiO_2)
- Process:
 - Mixing of Elium®, IL, and additives adding initiator (IL:PMMA (w/w%): 10:90 to 60:40)
 - Curing at 35 °C for 2 hrs
 - Post-curing at 80°C for 1 hr

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Electrolyte - SEM

Electrolyte - Material characterization

DSC

DMTA

Tensile test

Ionic liquid %	Tensile modulus (GPa)
0	2.63
10	2.55
25	2.34
20	2.06
25	1.70
30	1.12

ASTM D638- type V

Electrolyte - Conductivity - EIS

Supercapacitor Device Fabrication

- Electrode and separator (*Greenhalgh's group**)
 - Carbon fibre: Carbon-aerogel-modified carbon fibre (C-weave, 200 gsm), CAG-CF
 - Separator: Glass fibre, GF
- Thin films of *IL50%+additives* is *in-situ* polymerized on the CAG-CF and GF.
- Thin films of *IL30%+additives* is hot-pressed on the initial device layout.

Supercapacitor Device Mechanical Performance

DMTA

Supercapacitor Device Electrochemical Performance

Cyclic voltammetry

Capacitance vs. Scan rate

- 5.2 F/g @ 1 mV/s Active mass
- 0.7 F/g @ 1 mV/s Device mass

Recycling

- Using ethyl-acetate as a solvent
- Simple and efficient method

Recycling- NMR

Recycling- Mechanical Test

>10% decrease
in modulus

Conclusion

- Optimization of the conductivity and mechanical performance should be considered simultaneously for an efficient structural polymer electrolyte.
- The integration of sustainability and recyclability should be seamlessly incorporated into the design process.
- Considering the capability of Elium® resin, the process has the potential of scaling up.

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Thank you!

Tensile

